

PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications

Deliverable D4.1

PILOTING first robotic vehicles

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Contents

1. Introduction	11
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	11
1.2 Scope of the document.....	11
1.3 Structure of the document.....	12
2. Aerial Robots.....	13
2.1 AEROX.....	13
2.1.1 General Overview	13
2.1.2 Components description	15
2.1.3 Technical Specifications.....	21
2.2 AERO-CAM	22
2.2.1 General Overview	22
2.2.2 Components description	24
2.2.3 Technical Specifications.....	27
2.3 VIAD-DRONE	28
2.3.1 General Overview	28
2.3.2 Components description	31
2.3.3 Technical Specifications.....	36
2.4 TTDRONE.....	36
2.4.1 General Overview	36
2.4.2 Component description.....	38
2.4.3 Technical Specifications.....	44
3. Ground Robots	45
3.1 RISING	45
3.1.1 General Overview	45
3.1.2 Components description	46
3.1.3 Technical Specifications.....	49
3.2 CART.....	50
3.2.1 General Overview.....	50

3.2.2	Components description	51
3.2.3	Technical Specifications.....	53
4.	Crawlers and hybrid robots	54
4.1	BIKE	54
4.1.1	General overview.....	54
4.1.2	Component description.....	56
4.1.3	Technical Specifications.....	62
4.2	HYBRID	65
4.2.1	General Overview	65
4.2.2	Components description	67
4.2.3	Technical Specifications.....	73
5.	Conclusions	75

List of Figures

Figure 1: AeroX aerial contact robot. The first and second version are shown in the upper part of the figure. The current PILOTING version is shown at the bottom of the figure.....	14
Figure 2: Hardware diagram of AeroX. Upper picture is the HW located in the airframe, and the bottom picture refers to the components located in the moving robotic arm.	16
Figure 3: Robotic contact device of AeroX robot.	17
Figure 4: End effector of AeroX robot.	17
Figure 5: Altair io360 gas sensor. The pictures shows multiple nodes and its communication base.	18
Figure 6: Ultrasonic Generator 110-LAN. Mistras Eurosonic.	18
Figure 7: AeroX roller probe for continuous monitoring of the surface.	19
Figure 8: Intel T265 stereo camera system.....	19
Figure 9: Ground communication system	19
Figure 10: Propellers' protection of the AeroX robot.	20
Figure 11: AeroX robot folded for easier transportation.	20
Figure 12: AERO-CAM aerial robot	22
Figure 13: Aerial robot hardware integration relative to the main added components	23
Figure 14. Hardware integration of the minimum components for manual flight.	24
Figure 15: DJI Matrice 600 Pro.....	24
Figure 16: Sony Alpha 7 IV	25
Figure 17: Gimball Gremsy T3 free volumen.	25
Figure 18: gimbal and camera integration on the UAV.	26
Figure 19: Damper system.....	26
Figure 20: LIDAR integration on the aircraft.....	27
Figure 21: VIAD-DRONE modular concept.....	29
Figure 22: Bearing inspection use case schematic.	29
Figure 23: Picture of the first prototype of the VIAD-DRONE with the bearing inspection configuration.....	30
Figure 24: Front view of the design for the sensor installation configuration.	31
Figure 25: Target installation use case schematic.	31

Figure 26: CAD of the base platform (left) and picture of the first prototype of the base platform.	32
Figure 27: Caterpillar system. CAD (left) and picture of the built system (right).	33
Figure 28: Cargo system. CAD (left) and picture of the built system (right).....	34
Figure 29: CAD of the manipulator for target installation mounted on the VIAD-DRONE. ...	34
Figure 30: Close-up view of the CAD of the retractile mechanism (left and center) and of the built prototype (right).	35
Figure 31: Ubiquity Bullet 5GHz.	35
Figure 32: Tunnel inspection robotic system integrates a UGV and a UAV.	37
Figure 33: CAD of the TTDRONE.	37
Figure 34: Elistair SAFE-T 2 ground module	38
Figure 35: Elistair SAFE-T 2 aerial module.....	39
Figure 36: Safety battery	39
Figure 37: Sony A6400 camera	40
Figure 38: E PZ 16-50mm F3,5-5,6 OSS lens (left) and Sony A6400 camera plus the lens (right)	40
Figure 39: Seagull #REC for autonomous control of Sony A6400 (left) and Sony dummy battery (right).....	41
Figure 40: Gremsy S1V3 gimbal alone (left) and with the Sony A6400 mounted (right)	41
Figure 41: TTDRONE and drone landing cone of CART	42
Figure 42: T-Motor MN4014 KV400 (left) and 16x6.4’’ carbon fiber blades (right)	43
Figure 43: Top and front view of TTDRONE.....	43
Figure 44: RISING mobile manipulator.....	45
Figure 45: Kinova Gen3 Arm.....	46
Figure 46: Bota System SenseOne Torque Sensor.....	47
Figure 47: Robotiq 2F gripper.....	47
Figure 48: Robosense B-Pearl lidar.....	47
Figure 49: Flir Duo Pro R.....	48
Figure 50: Intel® RealSense™ D435i.....	48
Figure 51: Intel T265.....	48
Figure 52: Delta Wireless Charger	49

Figure 53: ALTAIR® io360 Gas Detector	49
Figure 54: CART vehicle	50
Figure 55: Sony alpha 7R IV inspection camera	51
Figure 56: Gremsy T7 gimbal + Zion Arm dampener	51
Figure 57: FARO Focus Laser Scanner	52
Figure 58: Drone Landing, transport and Recharging area	52
Figure 59: Remote control and e-stop	53
Figure 60: Refinery vessel inspection configuration	54
Figure 61: BIKE inspection configuration	55
Figure 62: Refinery vessel Surface preparation configuration	55
Figure 63: BIKE cleaning configuration	56
Figure 64: Basic BIKE platform	57
Figure 65: BIKE DoF positions	57
Figure 66: BIKE steering range	58
Figure 67: Gas detection system	58
Figure 68: 3D Loc System	59
Figure 69: HDTZ1 inspection camera	60
Figure 70: Ultrasonic thickness measurement system	60
Figure 71: Pneumatic cleaning brush	61
Figure 72: Pneumatic control station	62
Figure 73: HYBRID aerial robot for the inspection of magnetic pipes. The first picture is the first version of the robot, and the rest correspond to the second version (PILOTING version).	66
Figure 74. Hardware components architecture of the Hybrid robot	68
Figure 75. Pictures of the landing gear	69
Figure 76. Satellite deployment system	69
Figure 77. Lidar integration for navigation and pipe detection.	70
Figure 78. Altair io360 gas sensor. The pictures shows multiple nodes and its communication base.	70
Figure 79. Ultrasonic Generator 110-LAN. Mistras Eurosonic.	71
Figure 80. Wireless communication system	71

Figure 81: Satellite description.....72

Figure 82: Satellite interfaces72

List of Tables

Table 1. Acronyms list	10
Table 2: Robotic vehicles, types and associated Use-Cases.....	11
Table 3: AEROX specifications	21
Table 4: AERO-CAM specifications.....	27
Table 5: Estimation of the weight of the VIAD-DRONE	32
Table 6: Technical specification for VIAD-DRONE.....	36
Table 7: Estimation of the weight of the TTDRONE.....	42
Table 8: Technical specification of TTDRONE.....	44
Table 9: RISING technical specifications	49
Table 10: CART technical specifications	53
Table 11: BIKE technical specifications	62
Table 12: HYBRID specifications.....	73

Acronyms

Table 1. Acronyms list

Abbreviation	Explanation
API	Application programming interface (software)
BPL	Broadband Over Powerline
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line of Sight
CAD	Computer aided design (software)
CATEC	Advanced Center for Aerospace Technologies (Partner)
CoM	Center of Mass
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
GCS	Ground Control Station
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system a general term describing any satellite constellation that provides positioning, navigation, and timing service
GSD	The Ground Sampling Distance, distance between two consecutive pixel centers measured on the ground
HW	Hardware
IMU	Inertial measurement unit (sensor)
LIDAR	Light detection and ranging (sensor)
Mpx	Megapixel, also MP, number of pixel in a picture, indication of resolution.
MTOM	Maximum take-off mass
MTOW	Maximum take-off weight
RBNK	Robotnik Automation S.L.L. (Partner)
RC	Remote controlled (vehicles)
RMCP	Robotic Mobile Contact Platform
RPAS	Remotely Piloted Aircraft System
SDK	Software Development Kit, a group of tools that enable the programming of mobile applications
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle
USE	University of Sevilla (Partner)
UT	Ultrasonic testing
UTM	Ultrasonic thickness measurement
WTR	Waygate Technologies Robotics (Partner)

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document describes the first iteration of the robotics vehicles ready to integrate within the PILOTING I&M platform, describing each robotic vehicle's configuration and major characteristics.

1.2 Scope of the document

The D4.1 “PILOTING first robotic vehicles” deliverable covers the activities carried out within the WP4 “Adaptation of robotic vehicles and data gathering” to adapt and develop the PILOTING robotic vehicles (aerial robots, ground robots and crawlers and hybrid robots) during the first period of the project.

Multiple robotic vehicles are covered under each type. Table 2 lists the robotic vehicles covered by each scenario as they were identified in the deliverable D3.1.

Table 2: Robotic vehicles, types and associated Use-Cases

Robotic vehicle	Type	Use-case scenario
AEROX	Aerial vehicle	Refinery large structures inspection
AERO-CAM	Aerial vehicle	Viaduct general visual inspection
VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle	Viaduct bearing inspection
		Viaduct sensor installation
		Viaduct surveying target installation
TT-DRONE	Aerial vehicle	Tunnel local inspection
RISING	Ground vehicle	Refinery ground monitoring
CART	Ground vehicle	Tunnel general inspection
BIKE	Crawler	Refinery vessel inspection
HYBRID	Hybrid	Refinery pipes inspection

1.3 Structure of the document

This deliverable has been structured by type of robot, divided in aerial vehicles, ground vehicles, crawlers, and hybrid systems. Therefore, the document presents the following sections:

- Section 1 specifies the purpose, scope and structure of the document.
- Section 2 describes the adaptations and development done in relation to the aerial robots, containing AEROX, AERO-CAM, VIAD-DRONE and TTDRONE drones.
- Section 3 describes the adaptations and development done in relation to the ground robots, containing RISING and CART robots.
- Section 4 describes the adaptations and development done in relation to crawlers and hybrid robots, containing BIKE and HYBRID robots.

2. Aerial Robots

2.1 AEROX

2.1.1 *General Overview*

The AeroX aerial contact robot is a specialised aircraft capable of contacting static surfaces. This UAV is composed of two different platforms: the aerial platform and the Robotic Mobile Contact Platform (RMCP), which will be in charge of the UT inspection. The RMCP is attached at the end of the contact device of the aerial platform.

AeroX is a novel aerial robotic manipulator that performs physical contact inspection with unprecedented capabilities. It is composed of a robotic vehicle, a six degree-of-freedom (DoF) robotic arm, and a robotic end-effector equipped with wheels and inspection sensors. AeroX has a semi-autonomous operation, which provides interesting advantages in contact inspection. In the free-flight mode, the pilot guides the robot until performing contact with its end-effector on the surface to be inspected. During contact, AeroX is in its fully-autonomous GNSS-free contact-flight mode, in which the robot keeps its relative position with respect to the surface contact point using only its internal sensors. During autonomous flight, the inspector can move –with uninterrupted contact– the end-effector on the surface for accurately selecting the points where to perform inspections with sensors that require to be in contact or very close to the surface. The AeroX controller is able to efficiently compensate perturbations thanks to its design, which transmits the surface contact forces and perturbations to the robot center of mass and allows small movements of the aerial part of the robot in every DoF to absorb other perturbations such as wind. AeroX adopts a 4 coaxial rotor configuration and a simple and efficient design, which provides high stability, manoeuvrability, and robustness to rotor failure. It can perform contact inspection on surfaces at any orientation, including vertical, inclined, horizontal top or horizontal bottom and, its operation can be easily integrated into current maintenance operations in many industries.

Figure 1: AeroX aerial contact robot. The first and second version are shown in the upper part of the figure. The current PILOTING version is shown at the bottom of the figure.

The initial AeroX robot was designed a few years ago and, in the PILOTING project, it is facing its third major update (see Figure 1). At the beginning of the project, the second version of the robot has been used to validate the needed changes to elevate the TRL of the robot, and also, to execute experiments and operations in order to gain experience. These modifications have been performed in a design phase, and now, the new updated robot is being manufactured. However, due to the COVID-19 restrictions, the manufacture of the robot has been delayed, but it is expected to be finished and flying in the next months. Moreover, we also count with a previous version of the aerial robot (Aerov2), with the required modifications, to perform if needed, PILOTING experiments until the new version v3 is ready. The main changes performed in the last version (v3) with respect to the previous one (v2) are:

- **Structural robustness:** The robot is now more robust and resistant to accidental hits. Furthermore, the robustness of the robotic arm makes the robot more accurate during the contact operations due to the better estimation of its position.
- **Design changes for easier maintenance:** The cabling is now more accessible, so it could be changed in case any problem arises. Additionally, the structure is easier to mount and,

therefore, easier to perform than regular or accidental maintenance. This means that the aerial robot is designed in a better modular way, allowing to change independent subcomponents.

- Easier transportation and deployment: The previous AeroX robot had to be disassembled to reduce its size for transport. The arms connecting the motors with the structure were removed. The last version of the robot can now fold using a mechanism, allowing it to be easily transported and deployed once taken outside its box.
- Sensors integration for relative movements over the surface: A relative localisation sensor will be fused with the wheels movements encoders to obtain a relative mapping of the UT measurements.
- Dust and light rain fairing: The dust and light rain fairing has been updated to a newer system that is easier to install and remove and, at the same time, it protects the electronics of the robot.
- Gas detection system: The previous gas detection system was a very basic beeper that makes noise in case of detecting gases. The new system can be connected to a gas sensor network and to any device on the ground or even remotely, so the gas could be connected using multiple options to many centralised alarm systems.

Furthermore, a new version of the inspection tool is also being developed. Its main characteristics are:

- Automatic couplant application for faster UT inspection: The coupling gel is now automatically delivered to simplify the inspection operation.
- Surface cleaning: A surface cleaning tool can be installed to remove dirt or rust.
- Complete teleoperation: The inspection system can be controlled remotely and the electronics configuration chosen will allow to control it automatically.
- Video feed: A continuous video feed is received in the ground control station to allow the inspector to verify the correct coupling of the UT sensor.
- New soft materials for wheels and arm connection: New kind of materials are used to guarantee better docking between the inspection tool and the inspected surface.
- New continuous UT sensor integrated, capable of non-stop measuring and using less couplant gel.

2.1.2 Components description

The hardware diagram of AeroX is presented in Figure 2. The main components are defined below.

Figure 2: Hardware diagram of AeroX. Upper picture is the HW located in the airframe, and the bottom picture refers to the components located in the moving robotic arm.

Contact device

It is responsible for providing the capability of stationary contact with surfaces. It is a mechatronic device with six DoF and has the robotic end-effector at its end. Due to its efficient design, surface

contact forces are transmitted to the center of mass (CoM) of the aerial robot, enabling efficient and effective compensation.

Figure 3: Robotic contact device of AeroX robot.

End Effector

The robotic end-effector. It is located at the end of the robotic contact device and is endowed with wheels for moving on the surface under inspection. It integrates the sensors to be used for inspection and also additional sensors to facilitate operation, e.g., a camera for helping the operator identify the defects under inspection. A variety of robotic end-effectors can be mounted on the robotic contact device in order to use different sensors, change the motion on the surface of the robotic end-effector or even change the type of docking to the surface.

Figure 4: End effector of AeroX robot.

Gas sensor

The ALTAIR® io360 Gas Detector offers four-gas detection for high-risk areas, including confined spaces, perimeter and general area monitoring. The ALTAIR io360 combines the simple set-up of a smart home device, while allowing local or remote monitoring of hazardous areas. The ultra-long battery life keeps the focus on safety and less on maintenance. The ALTAIR io360 delivers IP68 ruggedness and best-in-class, XCell sensors, the performance expected from MSA.

Figure 5: Altair io360 gas sensor. The pictures shows multiple nodes and its communication base.

UT system

The 110 LAN is an ultrasonic device allowing to perform long-range ultrasonic measurement. Power supply and data transfer are performed by the mean of Ethernet communication. The 110 LAN device is compliant with the whole software developed by Mistras. The 110 LAN ultrasonic device focuses on the latest microelectronic evolution to comply with industrial ultrasonic assessment requirements. The device is developed to match the need of long-range ultrasonic application (up to 100m without repeater).

This device is used with the software EuroscanV and UTWin both developed by Mistras. Their use allows performing A/B/C Scan acquisition.

Figure 6: Ultrasonic Generator 110-LAN. Mistras Eurosonic.

UT roller sensor

The selected sensor is a dual crystal dry coupling roller probe. This sensor has a frequency of 4.0 MHz and a tolerance of 0.4 MHz. The coupling material of the tire is a black aqualene 365. This probe makes it possible to perform continuous measurements of the structure. Traditional probes are punctual and require applying coupling gel nearly every time a measurement is going to be taken. The minimum material thickness of this probe is 3 mm, and the maximum is 100mm.

Figure 7: AeroX roller probe for continuous monitoring of the surface.

Intel T265

The intel T265 is a stereo camera system that provides a relative positioning estimation. This camera can be integrated standalone or in conjunction with others. This multiple camera system can provide reliability to the positioning estimation.

Figure 8: Intel T265 stereo camera system

Robust communications system

The Ubiquity Rocket ac system is configured using a spectrum analyser working close to metallic structures. This allows to configure the system to its optimum performance for working surrounded of metallic tanks and other structures common in refineries.

Figure 9: Ground communication system

Propellers' protection

A robust propeller protection structure has been included in this last version of the aerial robot. Several tests have been performed with numerous designs of protective structures. The selected one avoid major wind disturbance and at the same time gives really good protection against accidental light impacts.

Figure 10: Propellers' protection of the AeroX robot.

Mechanical folding system for easier transportation

The folding system for easier transportation has been exclusively designed for this new robot. This system will make it possible to rotate the motor arms and position them in a way that the size of the robot is significantly reduced. This is important for quick storage and deployment. Furthermore, this functionality is useful in case the access to the asset to be inspected requires a smaller size of the robot before reaching the take-off area.

Figure 11: AeroX robot folded for easier transportation.

2.1.3 Technical Specifications

Table 3: AEROX specifications

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
RLS-Spec-01	Size of the robot (in mm) <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>
RLS-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
RLS-Spec-03	Maximum takeoff weight: 25 Kg
RLS-Spec-04	Empty weight without batteries and contact device: 9 Kg
RLS-Spec-05	Weight with standard equipment and batteries: 18 Kg
RLS-Spec-06	Free-flight positioning precision using GNSS: Vertical 0,5 m, horizontal 1,5 m.
RLS-Spec-07	Maximum wind resistance during contact: gusts of over 10 m/s
RLS-Spec-08	Standard configuration flight time: 10 min
RLS-Spec-09	Minimum surface curvature: 0,5 m radius
RLS-Spec-10	Batteries specifications: 2 units of 6S (25 V) and 22 Ah capacity.
RLS-Spec-11	Wireless communications over proprietary ubiquity Wi-Fi protocol.
RLS-Spec-12	Cable communications over ethernet gigabit cable.
RLS-Spec-13	UT sensor dual crystal probe
RLS-Spec-14	UT sensor frequency 4 MHz
RLS-Spec-15	UT sensor element diameter 8 mm
RLS-Spec-16	UT sensor surface temperature 0°C ... 40°C
RLS-Spec-17	UT sensor wall thickness range 3 ... 100 mm

RLS-Spec-18	UT instrument Mistras 110-LAN
RLS-Spec-19	UT software EuroscanV

2.2 AERO-CAM

2.2.1 General Overview

The AERO-CAM RPAS is the aerial platform used for the visual inspection of the viaduct. The UAV is based on a DJI Matrice 600 Pro customised for the mission. The current version of the UAV is shown in Figure 12, where it can be seen the CAD model of the drone and its final implementation. As it can be seen, the configuration of the UAV is a 6-motors UAV, so the aircraft is robust against the failure of one engine due to the redundancy achieved by the configuration.

Figure 12: AERO-CAM aerial robot

The aerial robot is being designed as small as possible, considering the weight and size. Moreover, the flight time has been optimised, maximising its endurance to achieve the required flight times with the needed payload, which in that case are the camera and localisation sensors.

The AERO-CAM operates in BVLOS, and the camera is integrated on top of the aircraft, allowing to take photos of the underside of the viaduct deck and having cleaner pictures of the horizontal surfaces of the pillar and the rest of the possible walls. The electronics of the UAV incorporates an electronic cover for dust protection. Due to the expectable loss of GNSS signal under the viaduct, AERO-CAM integrates a LIDAR underneath the airframe, between the two legs of the landing skid.

Regarding the hardware architecture for integrating the camera in charge of the visual inspection, two Wi-Fi antennas are integrated on-board the aerial robot. These antennas allow the communication between the main computer, located at the bottom of the aircraft, and the computer of the camera system. The schematic of the hardware integration of the camera and the localisation sensors is shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13: Aerial robot hardware integration relative to the main added components

Figure 14. Hardware integration of the minimum components for manual flight.

2.2.2 Components description

Airframe DJI Matrice 600 Pro

The airframe used for the AERO-CAM is a customised DJI Matrice 600 Pro, a six motors UAV with a demonstrated robustness against the failure of one rotor. It has a modular design, making the integration of new units easy and fast. This Pro version of the Matrice 600 improves the endurance and the capacity for the payload with respect to its basic version. It is equipped with the A3 Pro autopilot, with the transmission system Lightbridge 2 HD, as well as with intelligent batteries. In Figure 15 it can be seen a regular Matrice 600 Pro UAV, and the customised solution to create an AERO-CAM.

Figure 15: DJI Matrice 600 Pro

The UAV is equipped with a GNSS receiver, consisting in three redundant antennas, as well as with a 9-axis IMU that works at 400 Hz.

Camera

The selected camera for the inspection is the Sony alpha 7R IV. This camera is a full-frame retroilluminated camera with 61 Mpx, 10 fps and ISO 32000. Depending on the used lens, it can achieve a GSD until 0.1 mm. The manufacturer provides as well with an API that allows the operator to use it for remote shooting.

Figure 16: Sony Alpha 7 IV

Gimbal and damper system

The camera is mounted on a gimbal, particularly the Gremsy T3. It is one of the most advanced 3-axis camera stabilisers in the market. This gimbal ensures a simple and clean setup. Its has the perfect volume for the selected camera allocation. The free volume for the camera is the one shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Gimbal Gremsy T3 free volumen.

As it was said before, the gimbal has been mounted on the top of the airframe, in order to cover all the required surfaces: bottom of the viaduct desk and horizontal surfaces of the pilar. The final integration of the gimbal and the camera on the airframe is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: gimbal and camera integration on the UAV.

As it can be seen in the image above, the gimbal is not mounted directly on the airframe, but on a customised damper. This damper reduces the vibrations transmitted to the system while flying, what makes the visual inspection system even more robust and stable. This integration will ensure that the pictures will have the required resolution. The damper system can be seen in more detail in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Damper system

LIDAR

To improve the situational awareness due to the loss of GNSS signal while the UAV is flying underneath the viaduct, the UAV has been equipped with a LIDAR. This LIDAR will be used to obtain a reliable localisation to close the control loop once the GNSS signal is not available or degraded. The selected LIDAR is the Ouster LIDAR sensor, model OS0 with 128 channels. Its integration on the aircraft is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: LIDAR integration on the aircraft

Communications

As it was seen in Figure 13 and Figure 14, the communication on the aircrafts has two differentiated levels. The first one is on-board the aircraft, where the camera PC communicates with the aircraft’s PC core through Wifi. Then, at the second level, the aircraft communicates with the ground both with the RC receiver with the pilot and with the Ubiquity module installed on-board and on the GCS.

2.2.3 Technical Specifications

Table 4: AERO-CAM specifications

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
AC-Spec-01	<p>Size (in mm)</p>
AC-Spec-02	MTOM 15.5 kg

AC-Spec-03	Stationary flight accuracy in P-GPS mode: Vertical: ± 0.5 m, Horizontal: ± 1.5 m
AC-Spec-04	Maximum climb speed: 5 m/s
AC-Spec-05	Maximum descend speed: 3 m/s
AC-Spec-06	Maximum wind resistance: 8 m/s
AC-Spec-07	Maximum speed: 60 km/h without wind
AC-Spec-08	Maximum endurance: 32 min without payload, 16 min with maximum payload.
AC-Spec-09	Battery type LiPo 6s
AC-Spec-10	Operational temperature (for the batteries): from -10°C to 40°C
AC-Spec-11	61 MPx camera
AC-Spec-12	Camera ISO from 100 to 32000
AC-Spec-13	Two available lenses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General inspection: SONY ZEISS SONNAR 24/1.8 • Detailed inspection: SONY FE 85/1.8 (up to 0.1mm GSD)
AC-Spec-14	Full coverage of vertical surfaces
AC-Spec-15	Full coverage of horizontal and sloping surfaces
AC-Spec-16	Bottom surfaces partially covered
AC-Spec-17	No restrictions to fly far away distance from obstacle while GNSS is available
AC-Spec-18	In GNSS denied mode, range of flying far away from obstacles: 50m (LIDAR range)
AC-Spec-19	Minimum allowed distance to obstacle: ~ 3 m front, ~ 2.5 m overhead

2.3 VIAD-DRONE

2.3.1 General Overview

The VIAD-DRONE is a specialised aerial platform designed to adapt to different inspection applications for viaducts. The envisioned applications in the PILOTING project for this platform are the bearings inspection, the sensor box installation and the target installation. More details about these use cases can be found in deliverable D3.2. All these applications have one thing in common, the aerial robot interacts physically with the viaduct structure, sometimes needing to get close to narrow spaces like the one between the top of the pillar and the deck. Thus, this platform should be as small as possible to access the narrow spaces but powerful enough to carry the necessary tools to interact with the viaduct structure. The proposed solution is a modular design, in which the same base platform

can be adapted with some accessories to fulfil the specific needs of each use case. Figure 21 shows the modular concept of the platform with the three main accessories, one for each use case.

Figure 21: VIAD-DRONE modular concept.

The base platform, common for every configuration, includes the airframe with the electronics and batteries, the onboard computer, the communications system, and the navigation sensors.

Bearing inspection configuration

Viaduct bearings are in a difficult place to access, very often in a 30 to 60 cm space between the top of the pillar and the deck of the viaduct. Therefore, it is challenging to perform a visual inspection, specially of the inner sides of the bearings. The proposed solution to overcome this challenge is for the aerial robot to be able to attach to the deck and, thanks to a caterpillar system, crawl towards the bearings to get closer images. Figure 22 shows a schematic of the application, with the aerial robot approaching the bearings.

Figure 22: Bearing inspection use case schematic.

Apart from the caterpillar system, this configuration includes an inspection camera stabilised with a gimbal. This camera-gimbal system is placed at the bottom of the platform, below the central plate.

Figure 23 shows a picture of the first built prototype of the VIAD-DRONE with this configuration. The inspection camera is not yet installed.

Figure 23: Picture of the first prototype of the VIAD-DRONE with the bearing inspection configuration.

Sensor installation configuration

This configuration is very similar to the previous one, as it also includes the caterpillar system. This is necessary because the sensor boxes should be installed on top of the pillars, and crawling is the safest way to access this narrow space.

However, instead of an inspection camera, this configuration includes a cargo system, able to carry and deploy the sensor box. This cargo system is placed below the central plate. Figure 24 shows the front view of the design of this configuration, where the caterpillar system is on the upper part of each side, the cargo system is below the central plate, and the sensor box is at the bottom, already released from the system.

Figure 24: Front view of the design for the sensor installation configuration.

Target installation configuration

The targets are installed on vertical surfaces like the pillar walls. Therefore, this configuration does not need the caterpillar system. Nonetheless, it still needs to establish contact with the viaduct structure, more accurately with the pillars. This configuration then needs a contact system with a manipulator to stick the targets to the pillars.

Figure 25 shows a schematic of this use case, with the aerial robot performing a touch-and-go manoeuvre to install the target on a vertical surface.

Figure 25: Target installation use case schematic.

2.3.2 Components description

Base platform

The base platform is an octorotor in a coaxial configuration with 14'' propellers. The selected motors are the T-Motor MN4014 KV400. The power supply is comprised of two 6S 4500 mAh LiPo

batteries, allowing an estimated flight time of 10 minutes with the MTOM. The platform also includes a CUAV flight controller running PX4 autopilot firmware.

The airframe includes a couple of parallel bars, used to attach the different add-ons like the caterpillar system or the manipulator for target installation. Figure 26-left shows a CAD drawing of the base platform. Figure 26-right shows a picture of the first built prototype of the base platform with the bars.

Figure 26: CAD of the base platform (left) and picture of the first prototype of the base platform.

Table 5 summarises the estimated weights of the different components and the sum of all which corresponds to the maximum take-off weight (MTOW).

Table 5: Estimation of the weight of the VIAD-DRONE

Component	Weight (g)
Frame + Motors	2700
Electronics	500
Batteries	1300
Add-on + Payload	Up to 3250
TOTAL	7750

Caterpillar system

This system allows the aerial robot to establish contact with upper horizontal surfaces like the bottom of the viaduct's deck and crawl through it. Although this system is heavier than just having a couple of motorised wheels, it is more robust to possible obstacles or imperfections on the surface such as small cracks or holes. Having more contact surface makes the aerial robot more stable in the contact.

It uses a commercial caterpillar, actuated by 12V DC motor, mounted on a custom carbon fiber structure. It is attached to the platform by the extremes of the add-on bars. Figure 27 shows a CAD of the caterpillar system and a picture of the system built.

Figure 27: Caterpillar system. CAD (left) and picture of the built system (right).

Inspection camera

The inspection camera is only used for the bearing inspection use case. This camera should be able to take high-quality images of the bearings from a couple of meters. The images will be used to detect defects on the bearings.

The first idea was to use the same option as in AERO-CAM for the viaduct visual inspection, the Sony alpha 7R IV. However, the weight of the combined camera-gimbal system is too heavy for this platform. Therefore, the selected camera is the same as in the TTDRONE, the Sony A6400. It uses the CMOS Exmor® type APS C (23.5x15.6 mm) sensor and has a resolution of 24Mp (6000x4000 pixels). This camera weighs only 403g. Depending on the used lens, it can achieve a GSD until 0.1 mm.

The gimbal selected to stabilise this camera is the Gremsy S1V3. This gimbal has a weight of 830 g, so the full camera-gimbal system weighs 1233 g plus the lens, which fits with the MTOM of the platform.

Cargo system

This system is responsible for carrying the sensor box and deploying it at the specified location. It is composed of a carbon fiber structure with a big hole for the sensor box and two linear actuators to hold it in position when switched on and to free the cargo when switched off. Attaching points must be added to the sensor box to let the linear actuators fit. Figure 28-left shows a CAD drawing of the cargo system, in which one can identify the sensor box in the middle and the two linear actuators. The sensor box considered for the design is a standard 115x90x55 mm plastic box. However, the system will also work for taller boxes. This CAD also highlights two 3D printed adapters (in blue) which adapt the standard screw attaching system to the linear actuators. Figure 28-right shows a picture of the built cargo system upside down.

Figure 28: Cargo system. CAD (left) and picture of the built system (right).

Manipulator for target installation

The proposed design consists of a pole with a retractile mechanism on the tip, allowing to place the targets with a touch and go manoeuvre. Like the caterpillar system, it is attached to the add-on bars. Figure 29 shows the CAD of the manipulator for target installation mounted on the base platform.

Figure 29: CAD of the manipulator for target installation mounted on the VIAD-DRONE.

Figure 30 shows a close-up view of the CAD of the retractile mechanism. This mechanism absorbs the contact force, sticking the target to the vertical surface of the viaduct's pillar.

Figure 30: Close-up view of the CAD of the retractile mechanism (left and center) and of the built prototype (right).

Navigation sensors

When flying below and close to a viaduct, the GNSS signal might not be reliable enough to perform safe navigation. Moreover, the accuracy in the localisation is an important requirement for the system. Therefore, the aerial robot needs to rely on some sensors for localisation and safe navigation through the scenario. The selected sensors for this robot are two stereo cameras (one looking forward and the other looking down and back) and a 2D lidar with a mirror to detect at the same time the pillar and the deck.

Onboard computer and communication

An onboard computer is necessary for computing localisation and navigation algorithms besides inspection and mission control. This computer is connected to all the sensors and actuators on the robot, including the flight controller, and it is also in communication with the ground station through the communication system. The selected computer is an Intel NUC i7.

The communication system is a Ubiquity Bullet 5GHz (see Figure 31). This device allows reliable communication from the aerial robot to the ground station.

Figure 31: Ubiquity Bullet 5GHz.

2.3.3 Technical Specifications

Table 6: Technical specification for VIAD-DRONE.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
VD-Spec-01	Weight w/o payload: 5150g
VD-Spec-02	Maximum take-off weight (MTOW): 7750g
VD-Spec-03	Flight time with MTOW: 10 min
VD-Spec-04	Size (LxWxH): 802 x 928 x 280 mm
VD-Spec-05	Power supply: 2x 6S 4500 mAh LiPo batteries
VD-Spec-06	Minimum clearance for sensor deployment: 90cm (width) x 30cm (height)
VD-Spec-07	Size of the sensor box (LxWxH): 115 x 90 x 20-120 mm

2.4 TTDRONE

2.4.1 General Overview

The TTDRONE vehicle is an aerial robot that is part of the platform dedicated to the tunnel inspection use case. This tunnel inspection platform is formed by an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV), which is described in section 0, and an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), described in detail in the present section. This platform is represented in Figure 32. This platform aims to perform an exhaustive inspection of a tunnel by taking several images, which will be analysed by artificial intelligence algorithms to detect possible defects in the tunnel structure.

Figure 32: Tunnel inspection robotic system integrates a UGV and a UAV.

The UGV, named CART, is the responsible of performing the general inspection of the tunnel. The UAV will perform the local inspection by taking closer images and accurate measurements in the inspection points that the ground robot cannot reach.

The UAV is connected to the UGV through a tethered system. That means that both power and data are transmitted from the UGV to the UAV by means of a cable connection. The aerial robot is known as the TTDRONE, which stands for Tunnel Tethered DRONE.

Figure 33 shows the CAD of the first design of the TTDRONE. As of writing this document, due to delays in international purchases, there is no built prototype of the TTDRONE. In any case, it will be ready for the integration and first round of experiments on the field planned for the next year. Each of the components of this platform are described in the following section.

Figure 33: CAD of the TTDRONE.

2.4.2 Component description

Tethered System

One of the main requirements of this aerial robot is to have the capacity of flying for extended periods of time. Tethered systems become the perfect solution to accomplish this requirement since these systems can provide continuous power to the UAV. If the tethered system is connected to an infinite power source, the flying time of the UAV will be only limited by the overheating of motors.

The tethered system employed in this platform is the Elistair SAFE-T 2. This system can supply up to 2200W of continuous power to the UAV, being able to reach a 2800W peak for 3 seconds. To do so, the system must be connected to a 220-250VAC 50-60Hz power source. Figure 34 shows the ground module of this tethered system. This module weighs 25kg and its dimensions are 610x410x265mm.

Figure 34: Elistair SAFE-T 2 ground module

The length of the micro-tether permits the UAV to reach a maximum height of 100 meters. Nevertheless, in the tunnel local inspection application the maximum length of the tether will be constrained. The tether weighs 25g/m. The Elistair SAFE-T 2 includes a tensioning control system that permits to control the tension of the tether in any time, even during the flight. The tension of the tether can be controlled manually, remotely through an Android application or by means of the SDK (Software Development Kit).

In addition to the power supply, the micro-tether also includes a fiber optic cable that permits to send and receive data to the UAV at a speed of 200Mb/s. Also, the system permits to transmit data through the power cable by using the BPL (Broadband Over Powerline) method.

The Elistair SAFE-T 2 has an SDK where the user can control the power, cable torque and program alarms, and can monitor the power consumption, the tether unwound, the tether speed, the temperature and the flight duration.

The aerial module, which is placed on-board the UAV, is used to rectify the voltage received through the power cable to the voltage needed for the UAV electronics; in this case 6S (24v). This aerial module is shown in Figure 35. It weighs 0.7kg and their dimensions are 168x109x54mm.

Figure 35: Elistair SAFE-T 2 aerial module

It is important to notice that the power that the tethered system can supply will limit the weight of the UAV. Therefore, the selection of the rest of the components of the UAV is constrained to this maximum weight and power consumption restrictions.

Safety battery

Even it would be a very rare event, a failure of the tethered system could occur during a flight of the UAV, which would certainly cause an accident. Hence, it is of utmost importance to include a safety battery on-board the vehicle that permits to have enough flight time to land the UAV safely. It has been considered that the adequate battery to accomplish this task must have a capacity of at least 1000mAh and a minimum discharge power of 100C (2400W). A battery of these characteristics weighs around 100 grams. Figure 36 shows an example of this type of battery.

Figure 36: Safety battery

Inspection camera and gimbal

The main requirement of this use case regarding the inspection camera is to ensure a precision of 0.1mm/pixel of the inspection images. To achieve this requirement the camera must have the highest possible resolution. However, this camera has also a weight restriction due to the limited power that the tethered system can supply. The selection of the camera and gimbal system was made considering this trade-off between having high resolution images and a lightweight system. Different types of cameras were considered, such as drone video cameras, industrial cameras, compact photography cameras, DSLR cameras or EVIL cameras. After analysing each type of camera, it was concluded that EVIL cameras (mirrorless) are the most adequate solution for this use case in order to fulfil the desired image precision while having low weight.

The selected camera is the Sony A6400, shown in Figure 37. It uses the CMOS Exmor® type APS C (23.5x15.6 mm) sensor and has a resolution of 24Mp (6000x4000 pixels). This camera is able to take images at a ratio of up to 11fps. The Sony A6400 weighs 403g.

Figure 37: Sony A6400 camera

The Sony A6400 camera comes with no lens and is only compatible with type E lenses. The selected lens for this particular use case is the E PZ 16-50mm F3.5-5.6 OSS, shown in Figure 38-left. It weighs 116g. Figure 38-right shows the Sony A6400 camera with this lens integrated. The lens was selected considering that images will be taken at a distance of 1 meter to the tunnel walls and that the GSD (Ground Sample Distance) must be less or equal to 0.1mm/pixel. The GSD is an image precision indicator that is defined as the distance between pixel centres measured on the ground (wall in this case) covered in an image. This lens has an optical zoom which permits to cover different focal length (16-50mm). With a fixed focal length of 40mm and taking the image at 1m distance to the wall, the GSD obtained with this camera setup is of 0.098mm/pixel. Thus, the precision requirement is achieved. The image footprint (covered wall area) obtained in these conditions is of 588x392mm. Furthermore, it is important to mention that it was ensured that with this focal length it is possible to focus the image at a distance of 1m to the wall (minimum focus distance of this lens with a 40mm focal length is of 0.3m).

Figure 38: E PZ 16-50mm F3,5-5,6 OSS lens (left) and Sony A6400 camera plus the lens (right)

To have the ability of taking images autonomously, it is necessary to control the operation of the camera from the onboard PC of the UAV. To do so, the Seagull #REC device will be used (Figure 39-left). This device has different digital inputs that permit to control the shutter, the zoom and other specifications of the camera. Furthermore, the Sony dummy battery (Figure 39-right) will be used to

connect the power of the camera to the power supply of the UAV in such a way that the Sony A6400 will have unlimited power.

Figure 39: Seagull #REC for autonomous control of Sony A6400 (left) and Sony dummy battery (right)

- The Gremsy S1V3 gimbal will be used to attach the camera to the UAV and to control its angles. This gimbal, shown in
- Figure 40, has a weight of 830g and its dimensions are 150x168x220mm. Its maximum payload is of 750g.

Figure 40: Gremsy S1V3 gimbal alone (left) and with the Sony A6400 mounted (right)

The Gremsy S1V3 permits a maximum angle speed of $180^\circ/s$ and has a range of $\pm 345^\circ$ on the yaw angle, of $\pm 120^\circ$ on pitch and of $\pm 45^\circ$ on roll. This gimbal has several types of communication connections (USB, CAN, JR, HDMI, SBUS and more) which facilitate the communication between the onboard PC and the camera. The gimbal can be controlled with either a commercial autopilot, such as PX4 or Ardupilot, or with the onboard PC using the Gremsy SDK.

LED light

Since some of the tunnels that will be inspected do not have any light (i.e., drainage tunnels), it will be necessary to include a light system in the TTDRONE. The light system is required, mainly, to provide more features to the visual odometry algorithms, which will be used in the localisation of the drone (see Deliverable D5.1). The light system will consist of a LED light located in the frontal part of the drone. The light system weighs around 200 grams since, even the light itself is lightweight, a huge sink is necessary to avoid the system reaching high temperatures.

Metal plate

The TTDRONE includes a metal plane in each of the legs. That is four metal plates, which weigh 50g each. These metal plates are needed to attach the vehicle to the drone landing cone located on the upper part of the CART vehicle (Sec. 3.2), which is equipped with electromagnets. Figure 41 shows a scheme with the TTDRONE and the drone landing cone of the CART ground vehicle.

Figure 41: TTDRONE and drone landing cone of CART

Motorisation

The motors that will be used in TTDRONE depend on the total weight of the platform. Table 7 shows an estimation of the weight of the TTDRONE platform considering the weight of each component (without including the rotors). In this table, the tethered system concept includes the aerial module and the weight of the cable, the inspection camera concept includes the camera, the lens, the Seagull device and the dummy battery, the gimbal concept includes the gimbal and the damping base to attach it to the drone's structure and the electronics concept include the perception sensors, the autopilot and the onboard PC. The total estimated weight of the platform is 4650g.

Table 7: Estimation of the weight of the TTDRONE

Component	Weight (g)
Tethered system	1000
Safety battery	150
Inspection Camera	600
Gimbal	900
Electronics	800
Frame	600
LED light	200

Metal plate	200
TOTAL	4250

Considering the estimated weight, the selected motors are the T-Motor MN4014 KV400 (Figure 42) with carbon fiber blades of 16x6.4 inches. With this configuration, the rotors are able to lift 5640g at 50% of throttle and 9520g at 75%. The power consumed by the motors at 50% of throttle is 506W. The total weight of the platform with the rotors included is 5386g.

Figure 42: T-Motor MN4014 KV400 (left) and 16x6.4'' carbon fiber blades (right)

TTDRONE airframe

Figure 43 shows the top and front views of the TTDRONE with some dimensions. The distance from the center of one rotor to the center of the opposite rotor is 640mm. The diameter of the TTDRONE including the blades is 1021mm. The height of the UAV including the gimbal and the camera is 421mm.

Figure 43: Top and front view of TTDRONE

2.4.3 Technical Specifications

Table 8: Technical specification of TTDRONE.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
TT-Spec-01	Weight: 5386g
TT-Spec-02	MTOW: 5640g
TT-Spec-03	Height: 421mm
TT-Spec-04	Diameter (including blades): 1021mm
TT-Spec-05	Distance motor to motor: 640mm
TT-Spec-06	24V power supply from the aerial module of tethered system
TT-Spec-07	Safety battery: 6S LiPo 1000mAh and 100C
TT-Spec-08	Motor power consumption: 506W in hover
TT-Spec-09	Inspection image resolution: 6000x4000 (24MP)
TT-Spec-10	GSD: 0.098mm/pixel (40mm focal length and 1m of distance to the wall)
TT-Spec-11	Inspection image footprint: 588x392mm (40mm focal length and 1m of distance to the wall)
TT-Spec-12	Gimbal maximum angle speed: 180°/s
TT-Spec-13	Gimbal maximum angle range: $\pm 345^\circ$ in yaw, $\pm 120^\circ$ in pitch and $\pm 45^\circ$ in roll

3. Ground Robots

3.1 RISING

3.1.1 General Overview

Figure 44: RISING mobile manipulator

RISING is a mobile manipulator specially designed for inspection and intervention. The concept aims for high mobility, robust, modular, easily transportable and easy to deploy robot platform.

In the context of PILOTING, redesigning the first version of the RISING mobile platform in order to comply with the application specifics has been the main issue targeted. It is important to remark that with the redesign came the need of manufacturing most of the robotic parts from scratch. The Covid pandemic has brought different challenges including the shortage of components; the providers delay due to personnel shortage and Robotnik's own difficulties at the point of assembling and manufacturing some of the parts.

In any case, the bulk of the prototype has been already assembled at the date of writing this document, and any delay coming from the manufacturing is now resumed to a shorter testing period, where new features must be tested and new sensors have to be assembled as for the original plan. These activities are somehow overlapping with the PILOTING integration works and should not be conditioning the next stages of the project.

Coming to those features, the key points of its V2 redesign targeting refinery inspections are:

- Updating manipulation capabilities with a versatile lightweight robotic arm (onboard electronics), wrist camera, torque sensor and gripper.
- Increasing the manoeuvrability of the robot by including a rear set of flippers, also upgrading the motors and motor controllers, aiming for better performance in rough terrains, slopes or steps.

- Including additional perceptions means with a 3d lidar and a thermographic camera. Improving the navigation performance thanks to IMU embedded cameras and tracking cameras.
- Revising the sealings and encapsulation of sensors together with the refrigeration capabilities of the robot looking for a higher IP protection.
- Adapting the battery for extended duration and easiness of recharging operations thanks to a detachable battery and wireless charger options.
- Addition of 4G based communication.
- Addition of use case specific gas mesh sensor.
- Addition of lightweight web-based Ground Control application for a basic control independent from which device will be used.

3.1.2 Components description

Kinova Gen3 Arm

- The kinova Gen3 is a modular and adaptable robotic arm for grasping and manipulation tasks with 6/7 DOF, a 4 mid-range continuous kg payload and 900mm reach, with a really low power consumption (36W). Its embedded control makes it easier to integrate but it also has a versatile end-effector interface module, 1kHz closed-loop control and integrated torque sensor.

Figure 45: Kinova Gen3 Arm

Bota System SenseOne Torque Sensor

- It is a 6 Axis Force Torque Sensor with precision. It is integrated with IMU for advanced applications in the automation and robotics industry. The EtherCAT output can deliver up to 1000 Samples per second. In addition, it is integrated with a 6-DoF IMU, Temperature sensors, IP67 and has a big range of power supply from 7 to 70 V. The SensONE is a one of its kind product and the best solution for force sensitive applications.

Figure 46: Bota System SenseOne Torque Sensor

Robotiq 2F gripper

- The robotiq 2F gripper is built for collaborative robots with two wide stroke options: 85 mm and 140 mm and a patented finger design enables both internal and external parallel gripping, as well as a unique encompassing grip mode.

Figure 47: Robotiq 2F gripper

Robosense B-Pearl lidar

- RS-Bpearl lidar is a 360°×90° Super Wide FOV, Short-range Blind Spot LiDAR. This device is a 32 line lidar with a range of 100m(30m@10% NIST) and horizontal/vertical resolution of 0.2-0.4° and 2.81° respectively.

Figure 48: Robosense B-Pearl lidar

Flir Duo Pro R

- The new FLIR Duo® Pro R combines a high resolution, radiometric thermal imager, 4K color camera, and a full suite of on-board sensors to bring you the most powerful dual-sensor imaging solution in the world for UxV's

Figure 49: Flir Duo Pro R

Flir PTU-5 unit

- Standing only six inches tall when fully integrated, the FLIR PTU-5 can hold up to 2250 grams on its top bracket, packing incredible performance into a compact package. Even with its small size the PTU-5 is more accurate than many other — more expensive — systems thanks to the absolute encoders used on the drive axes. Fully sealed and weatherproof rated to IP67, the PTU-5 can be used anywhere, even outdoors.

Intel D435i

- The Intel® RealSense™ D435i places an IMU into a cutting-edge stereo depth camera. With an Intel module and vision processor in a small form factor, the D435i is a powerful complete package that can be paired with customizable software for a depth camera capable of understanding its own movement.

Figure 50: Intel® RealSense™ D435i

Intel T265

- With its small form factor and low power consumption, the Intel® RealSense™ Tracking Camera T265 has been designed to give a good tracking performance straight off-the-shelf. Cross-platform, developer friendly simultaneous localisation and mapping for rapid prototyping needs.

Figure 51: Intel T265

Delta Wireless Charger

- The charger is a 1Kw charger that allows the robot to recharge its batteries without direct contact. In this way we are avoiding any spark risk in such a sensitive environment. The wireless charger includes a primary side (transmitter, TX) and a secondary side (receiver, RX). Secondary side includes Secondary-Pad (or On-Board-Pad, RX-Pad) and Secondary-Box (or On-Board-Electronics, RX-Box), both of them being installed in the robot while the primary side is part of the charging station.

Figure 52: Delta Wireless Charger

Battery LiFePo4 30Ah and casing

- An special design on the casing will allow us to detach the batteries easily, also thanks to rapid connectors in both sides.

Gas sensor:

- The ALTAIR® io360 Gas Detector offers four-gas detection for high risk areas, including confined spaces, perimeter and general area monitoring. The ALTAIR io360 combines the simple set-up of a smart home device, while allowing local or remote monitoring of hazardous areas. The ultra-long battery life keeps the focus on safety and less on maintenance. The ALTAIR io360 delivers IP68 ruggedness and best-in-class, XCell sensors, the performance expected from MSA

Figure 53: ALTAIR® io360 Gas Detector

3.1.3 Technical Specifications

Table 9: RISING technical specifications

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
RIS-Spec-01	860mm x 650mm x 250mm retracted flippers
RIS-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
RIS-Spec-03	Weight: 110 kg
RIS-Spec-04	48V 30A LiFePo4 Battery
RIS-Spec-05	4g and WiFi communication
RIS-Spec-06	IP65 protection class

RIS-Spec-07	Skid steering, 2 traction motors, 2 elevation motors
RIS-Spec-08	Max Speed: ± 2.5 m/s
RIS-Spec-09	Max Slope: 70%

3.2 CART

3.2.1 General Overview

Figure 54: CART vehicle

Robotnik's Cart vehicle shown in Figure 54 is a UGV based on an off-the-shelf electric cart.

With RWD Ackermann kinematics its traction is controlled by an AC motor with an incremental encoder and modifications have been done in order to control the direction through a power steering system with an absolute encoder.

Motion sensors are providing an odometry estimate for the vehicle. Together with different cameras, IMU's and Lidars, the robot can navigate autonomously or be teleoperated.

The vehicle allows an operator to take control anytime, even while sitting on it, but also implementing local and remote e-stop that actuate front and rear drum brakes.

In the context of the project, the main modifications are dealing with the inspection payload installed on the robot:

- Vertical crane for positioning inspection payload up to 3 meters.
- Gimbal and dampener for camera inspection.
- Rooftop landing and transport area for Drone local inspection solution.
- Additional GNSS denied navigation module.
- 3D Scanner mounting for inspection.

3.2.2 Components description

Inspection camera: Sony alpha 7R IV and 24/80 fixed focus.

- Full frame retroilluminated camera with 61 Mpx that will allow us to capture high-quality images of the defects. It is estimated that for the distances at which the robot will take the shooting we can obtain submillimeter per pixel images. The camera is also providing a new API that can be used for remote shootings.

Figure 55: Sony alpha 7R IV inspection camera

Crane:

- Robot installed crane is an ad-hoc lift column specially designed that can be fitted in the rear part of the vehicle. With a retracted height of near 800mm, its elongation can reach 1300, which is making possible to rise the inspection payload up to 3m. Its construction together with 48V motor and controller, and absolute position sensor makes possible to withstand a 50 kg payload even if it is 1m from its mass center.

Gremsy T7 gimbal + Zion Arm dampener

- Boasting a robust design and powerful motor, Gremsy T7 is the next level of heavy lifting gimbal for industrial applications. With a large camera cage and ability to carry up to 7 lbs, the T7 expands the range of compatible cameras and is capable of loading multiple specialised sensors at once. The selection of such gimbal comes also with the strong API provided but the device. Together with the gimbal a Zion Arm dampener will be installed in the crane in order to ease unwanted bounces while driving the vehicle.

Figure 56: Gremsy T7 gimbal + Zion Arm dampener

FARO laser scanner:

- FARO Focus Laser Scanners create accurate, complete and photorealistic 3D images of any environment or object in just a few minutes. The massive point cloud generated by the scanner (close to 1 million points per second with submillimeter error) will be used in order to find and evaluate defects in the tunnel structure. An specific mounting for such sensor is manufactured and installed in the vehicle, ensuring the widest possible field of view.

Figure 57: FARO Focus Laser Scanner

Drone Landing, transport and Recharging area

- This ad-hoc design fitting the vehicle rooftop includes a “cone” making it easier for the drone to land and be transported. A system of magnets is placed in order to hold the drone in place. The area can be used with a recharge pad or also manage the cable and wiring for a tethered drone.

Figure 58: Drone Landing, transport and Recharging area

Remote control and e-stop

- The remote control is directly linked to the robot providing priority velocity and steering commands but also hardware signals that can trigger a remote stop if needed.

Figure 59: Remote control and e-stop

3.2.3 Technical Specifications

Table 10: CART technical specifications

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
CA-Spec-01	Dimensions: 2.727 x 1.444 x 2.082 mm
CA-Spec-02	Weight: 800 Kg
CA-Spec-03	Payload: 2 people + 227 kg in the rear box
CA-Spec-04	Speed: 35 Km/h
CA-Spec-05	Autonomy: Up to 70 km
CA-Spec-06	Temperature range: 0° to +40°C
CA-Spec-07	Maximum slope: 30%
CA-Spec-08	Batteries: Lead Acid 240Ah@48V
CA-Spec-09	Traction motors: 7,5 Kw AC
CA-Spec-10	Traction system: Ackermann, Rear Wheel / 4 XX

4. Crawlers and hybrid robots

4.1 BIKE

4.1.1 General overview

Inspection Configuration

The configuration of Figure 60 is used to perform inspections on the pressure vessel. Both the HD inspection camera and the ultrasound inspection system are mounted on the BIKE. An umbilical connects the crawler to the supply and control stations outside the asset. A pump feeds water as a coupling medium to the probe. A laptop is used as the general control station for the pilot and the Integrated Control Station (ICS) can be used by an Inspector to perform mission specific tasks. The ICS also acts as power supply to the robot. The Gas detection system is in line between the ICS and the BIKE. It is connected through the umbilical to the gas sensor on the crawler. In an event where a gas level past a set threshold is detected, the power and communication coming from the ICS is disconnected, rendering the crawler itself inert. The ATEX rated sensor on the BIKE however can remain in operation to continue monitoring gas levels.

Figure 60: Refinery vessel inspection configuration

The basic crawler platform is equipped with the 3D Loc sensor for localisation and the gas sensor to detect potentially dangerous concentrations of flammable gases. For inspection it also carries the HDTZ1 camera for visual examination and an ultrasound sensor and instrument for wall thickness measurements. Figure 61 shows the complete crawler assembly used in this configuration.

Figure 61: BIKE inspection configuration

Cleaning Configuration

This second configuration detailed in Figure 62 is used in case surface preparation prior to inspection is required. A pneumatically powered rotary brush is mounted on an arm in front of the BIKE. Pneumatic cylinders are used to hold the brush against the surface during cleaning or to lift it up for better manoeuvring. The required air supply is provided through the umbilical from a pneumatic control station located outside the asset. The control station, in turn must be connected to a tool air supply.

Figure 62: Refinery vessel Surface preparation configuration

Figure 63 is the crawler setup for this configuration featuring the basic platform with the localisation and gas sensor. Instead of the sensors used for inspection of the previous configuration, the pneumatic cleaning tool is attached to the side of the platform. The HDTZ1 inspection camera can still be mounted in parallel for navigation and work monitoring purposes.

Figure 63: BIKE cleaning configuration

4.1.2 Component description

BIKE platform

The basic BIKE platform as shown in Figure 64 provides the locomotion required to navigate in refinery vessels. The wheels are strong permanent magnets that keep the crawler attached to any ferromagnetic surface in any orientation even when additional sensor payload is mounted. Each wheel is individually powered by brushless DC motors equipped with high resolution incremental encoders. The front wheel axis is suspended in a gimbal with two degrees of freedom that allows all four wheels to stay in surface contact over a high range of surface diameters. Turning the wheels at different speeds causes the front axis to rotate by up to 90° to the left and right for steering. This basic platform is furthermore equipped with front and back facing fisheye cameras that aid remote navigation. LEDs are arrayed around these cameras for illumination of the confined space. The clearance between the two wheel axis of the BIKE enables its unique ability to cross over convex corners of up to 90° . Likewise does the clearance in front and behind enable crossings of concave corners of up to 90° . The entire assembly is rated and tested to IP67.

Figure 64: Basic BIKE platform

Figure 65 shows the magnetic wheel arrangement and the position and orientations of the gimbal and steering axis of the front wheels.

Figure 65: BIKE DoF positions

Figure 66 shows the range of motion of the steering and gimbal axis.

Figure 66: BIKE steering range

Gas detection system

The gas detection system (GDS2) is comprised of the LEL sensor mounted on the BIKE and the controller box shown in Figure 67. It is intended to be used as an additional increase in operational safety for the robotic system, BIKE. The system is connected between the robot power and communication supply and the robot umbilical. It automatically de-energises the robot if the concentration of combustible gas at the robot location exceeds a predefined percentage of the LEL.

Figure 67: Gas detection system

The system continuously monitors the concentration of combustible gas at the location of the sensor mounted on the BIKE. If the robot is de-energised due to a measured concentration above the set LEL

threshold, the system keeps monitoring the gas concentration. This is a safe process due to the explosion proof design of the used on-board gas sensor and sensor housing. The user/operator can decide what immediate actions to take. If the level goes down again (due to actions of ventilation or for other reasons), the user may manually re-activate the robot and continue working.

3D Loc

The 3D Loc module in Figure 68 is both a hardware and software extension for the BIKE. It features a 2D Hokuyo LIDAR and a high precision IMU. A 3D model of the asset and wheel odometry from the basic platform are combined to perform high accuracy continuous localisation of the crawler throughout the mission.

Figure 68: 3D Loc System

HDTZ1 Camera

This inspection camera shown in Figure 69 is another module that can be mounted on top of the BIKE. It features an HD imaging sensor and a 12x optical zoom. Spot and flood lights add additional illumination. Two parallel laser dots are integrated for sizing purposes. The integrated tilt axis together with the spot-turning of the platform is used to point the view in any direction.

Figure 69: HDTZ1 inspection camera

UT sensor & Instrument

The ultrasonic thickness measurement kit is a combination of the probe mounted between the front wheels and an instrument mounted to the side of the crawler as depicted in Figure 70. The probe is a roller design that allows continuous line scans when combined with the position information from the crawler. A raster path driving mode can combine multiple parallel line scans into a local grid scan. The onboard instrument keeps the cable length to the probe short for better signal quality.

Figure 70: Ultrasonic thickness measurement system

Only water as a coupling medium is supplied through the umbilical from a small pump located outside the asset.

Cleaning brush

Figure 71 shows the pneumatically powered tool for surface preparation. Its purpose is to remove debris and dust to enable subsequent visual imaging and improve surface coupling of the ultrasonic sensor for wall thickness measurements.

A rotary brush is mounted with its axis parallel to the surface. Brushes are exchangeable for different widths and wire thickness, density or materials depending on the application. The rotation is powered by a pneumatic motor along the side of the arm and connected to the brush axis with a bevel gear. The surface contact force is generated by pneumatic cylinders on both sides of the arms. The amount of force can either be controlled by adjustable air pressure or with fixed distance spacers on both sides of the brush. Having the cylinders act in the opposite direction will lift the entire assembly during travelling.

Figure 71: Pneumatic cleaning brush

In addition to the crawler mounted brush, there is also a control station shown in Figure 72. It is placed outside the asset and must be supplied with pressurised air from a compressor or tool air supply if available. A suitable particle filter and oil separator is integrated. The air supply to the brush motor can be turned on or off with a switch and the pressure can be adjusted with a regulator. The cylinders can likewise be controlled to extend, retract or remain in a neutral position. A pressure regulator can be used to adjust the force of the cylinders.

Figure 72: Pneumatic control station

4.1.3 Technical Specifications

Table 11: BIKE technical specifications

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
RV-Spec-01	Storage temperature: -20...+70 °C
RV-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
RV-Spec-03	Weight (without cables): 9.6 kg
RV-Spec-04	Speed: - 60 ... + 60 mm/s
RV-Spec-05	Diameter range of basic BIKE platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the minimum curvature required to move straight and with full steering inside a cylindrical shape (d500), • the minimum curvature required to move straight and with full steering, outside a cylindrical shape (D300), • the minimum curvature required to move straight with low steering, outside a cylindrical shape (D254),

<p>RV-Spec-06</p>	<p>Corner crossing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convex up to 90° • Concave up to 90°
<p>RV-Spec-07</p>	<p>Min. steering Radius 172 mm</p>
<p>RV-Spec-08</p>	<p>48V power supply via umbilical cable from external supply station</p>
<p>RV-Spec-09</p>	<p>ISC2 power consumption maximum 640W</p>
<p>RV-Spec-10</p>	<p>ICS2 input voltage 100 ... 240 VAC, 50 ... 60 Hz</p>
<p>RV-Spec-11</p>	<p>Gigabit Ethernet communication within system</p>
<p>RV-Spec-12</p>	<p>IP67 protection class</p>

<p>RV-Spec-13</p>	<p>Cleaning brush 8.3 l/s air consumption</p>
<p>RV-Spec-14</p>	<p>Cleaning brush width up to 100 mm</p>
<p>RV-Spec-15</p>	<p>Surface curvature range with cleaning brush mounted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Max. radius: Flat surface • Min. radius: 310mm <p>Dished vessel heads of diameters larger than 3000 mm have a corner radius above the minimum.</p>
<p>RV-Spec-16</p>	<p>Corner crossing with cleaning brush mounted</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concave: 45° • Convex: 90°
<p>RV-Spec-17</p>	<p>Manhole minimum diameter 400 mm when cleaning brush mounted.</p>

RV-Spec-18	UT sensor dual crystal probe
RV-Spec-19	UT sensor frequency 4 MHz
RV-Spec-20	UT sensor wall thickness range 3 ... 100 mm
RV-Spec-21	UT instrument Mistras 110-LAN
RV-Spec-22	UT software EuroscanV
RV-Spec-23	HDTZ1 inspection camera Full-HD resolution
RV-Spec-24	HDTZ1 inspection camera 10x optical zoom
RV-Spec-25	HDTZ1 inspection camera flood- & spotlights with adjustable intensity
RV-Spec-26	HDTZ1 inspection camera parallel laser points for size gauging

4.2 HYBRID

4.2.1 General Overview

The HYBRID aerial robot is a specialised aircraft for inspecting magnetic pipes. This UAV is composed of two different platforms: the aerial platform, and the crawler robot, or satellite, which will be in charge of the UT inspection. The Satellite robot is gathered in the aerial platform, and it is deployed over the pipe once the HYBRID has landed on the pipe and it is attached to it.

HYBRID is a novel aerial robot that performs UT measurement on non-insulated pipes. It is composed of two different robots, the aerial platform and the crawler that are integrated conforming a single aircraft. Its performance over the pipe is based on its magnetics capabilities; both installed on the landing platform and on the satellite. Hence, once the aerial robot lands on the pipe, the landing platform magnetically attaches to it, and the rotors of the UAV are shut off. Then, the satellite is deployed over the pipe, and it starts the inspection of the pipe by mean of the UT sensor installed underneath it. The design of the landing and attachment platform allows the robot to land with certain inaccuracy with respect to the axis of the pipe, i.e., some misalignments in yaw or y axis. The HYBRID will start flying close to the expected landing spot, and in most cases, it will have GNSS coverage. Then, it will fly in an autonomous way towards the selected pipe with its navigation based on the GNSS signal. Once it reaches the pipe of interest, the navigation will be based on the local GNSS-free navigation system, supported by the on-board sensors installed on the UAV, such as a Lidar. This GNSS-free navigation system will be operative during the whole flight, mapping the environment and avoiding any unexpected obstacle. Moreover, in case of flying underneath a rack of pipe and then, the GNSS signal could be degraded, the navigation will be based on that system. Once the HYBRID lands on the pipe and the magnetic attachments are activated. Then, the Satellite robot is deployed, and the inspection will start.

During the flight, the satellite is magnetically attached to a platform that is part of the drone landing gear. When landed on the pipe, the end of that platform comes in flush contact with the pipe in a

shallow angle, creating a path for the satellite to transition onto the pipe in circumferential direction. The satellite can then be navigated to the inspection location. Its differential drive and adaptive suspension allow it to freely manoeuvre on elbows, T-sections and straight pipes in any orientation. At the inspection location, a thickness measurement reading can be performed using the integrated ultrasound sensor. This sensor is specially designed to continuously measure while driving with little demand for coupling fluid, enabling the acquisition of line scans (B-Scan).

Once the inspection has finished, the Satellite robot will be gathered again on the aerial platform, and the HYBRID returns to the take-off and landing area. Once more, its autonomous navigation will be primarily based on the GNSS signal but supported by the map done before by the GNSS-free navigation signal.

Figure 73:HYBRID aerial robot for the inspection of magnetic pipes. The first picture is the first version of the robot, and the rest correspond to the second version (PILOTING version).

The initial HYBRID robot was designed a couple of years ago, and in PILOTING project it is facing a major update (see Figure 73). At the beginning of the project, the first version of the robot has been used to execute experiments and operations in order to gain experience. Then, this second version has integrated several modifications in a design phase to validate the needed changes to elevate the TRL of the robot. However, and due to the COVID-19 restrictions the manufacture of the robot has been delayed, but it is expected to be finished and flying in the next months. Moreover, we also count with a previous version of the HYBRID (v1), with the required modifications, to perform if needed,

PILOTING experiments until the new version v2 is ready. The main changes performed in the last version (v2) with respect to the previous one (v1) are:

- Structural robustness: The robot is now more robust and resistant to accidental hits, mainly due to the improvements performed on the center of mass of the robot.
- The landing stability has been improved due to the design of a new landing frame, which increase the robustness of the system while still respecting the space required for the satellite gathering.
- The deployment ramp for the satellite robot has been, at the same time, lightened and strengthened due to a new design which is gradually deployed once the operation of the robot starts.
- It has been integrated a new UT electronics, more reliable as well as the ones used in a real industrial case. Hence, the new UT sensor is not as basic as the previous one.
- One of the most relevant improvements has been integrating a Lidar on-board the UAV, providing it with both a GNSS-free localisation system and an obstacle avoidance system. It considerably increases the reliability and robustness of the navigation system, enhancing the HYBRID to fly in a fully autonomous way during its all operation.
- Design changes for easier maintenance: The cabling is now more accessible, so it could be changed in case any problem arises. Additionally, the structure is now easier to mount and therefore, easier to perform its regular or accidental maintenance. This means that the aerial robot is designed in a better modular way, allowing to change independent subcomponents.
- Dust and light rain fairing: The dust and light rain fairing has been updated to a newer system that is easier to install and remove and, at the same time, it protects the electronics of the robot.
- Gas detection system: The previous gas detection system was a very basic beeper that makes noise in case of detecting gases. The new system can be connected to a gas sensor network and to any device on ground or even remote, so the gas could be connected using multiple options to many centralised alarm systems.
- Improved heat sinking of the satellite drive motors for continuous operation.

4.2.2 Components description

The hardware diagram of Hybrid is presented in Figure 74. The main components are defined below.

Figure 74. Hardware components architecture of the Hybrid robot.

Satellite cable management

The satellite cable management system takes care of deploying and retrieving all the cable that connects the satellite with the aerial robot. For this objective, a rolling system is used. Furthermore, all the signals passing through the cable needs to be transmitted over an industrial-grade slip-ring. The slip-ring allows rotating freely, avoiding messing up with the cables.

Pipe-landing system

The pipe landing system has been modified to allows landing on smaller pipes. The curvature of the landing gear is really important to minimise the height of the robot over the pipe once landed. The main reason is to increase stability, so the center of mass of the robot is closer to the pipe, it will be more difficult to slip over its surface. The landing system has a set of magnets that consume energy during deactivation.

Figure 75. Pictures of the landing gear

Satellite deployment system

The new satellite deployment system fits better with a wide range of pipe diameters. This system holds the satellite during flight thanks to its ferromagnetic structure. Once the robot is on top of the pipe, the deployment system lowers the crawler robot. The metallic layer of this system has a final adaptive layer to adopt the form of the pipe. So, thanks to this system the satellite could be deployed and retrieved easily.

Figure 76. Satellite deployment system.

Navigation and pipe detection sensor

The 360 Ouster Lidar (OS0) has been integrated at the front of the robot. This location for the Lidar allows the robot a minimum field of view of 180 deg of the frontal area of the robot with a horizontal FOV of 90 deg. That will give the robot enough pointcloud information to perform an autonomous flight avoiding obstacles. Furthermore, a novel mirroring system has been designed to use the lasers pointing backwards (ahead the robot). Two mirrors have been integrated, one for looking upwards to avoid obstacles, and a second one looking downwards, to avoid obstacles and detect the pipe to land on.

Figure 77. Lidar integration for navigation and pipe detection.

Gas sensor

The ALTAIR® io360 Gas Detector offers four-gas detection for high-risk areas, including confined spaces, perimeter and general area monitoring. The ALTAIR io360 combines the simple set-up of a smart home device, while allowing local or remote monitoring of hazardous areas. The ultra-long battery life keeps the focus on safety and less on maintenance. The ALTAIR io360 delivers IP68 ruggedness and best-in-class, XCell sensors, the performance expected from MSA.

Figure 78. Altair io360 gas sensor. The pictures shows multiple nodes and its communication base.

UT system

The 110 LAN is an ultrasonic device allowing to perform long range ultrasonic measurement. Power supply and data transfer are performed by the mean of Ethernet communication. The 110 LAN device is compliant with the whole software developed by Mistras. The 110 LAN ultrasonic device focuses the latest microelectronic evolution to comply with the requirement of industrial ultrasonic assessment. The device is developed to match the need of long-range ultrasonic application (up to 100m without repeater).

This device is used with the software EuroscanV and UTWin both developed by Mistras. Their use allows to perform A/B/CScan acquisition.

Figure 79. Ultrasonic Generator 110-LAN. Mistras Eurosonic.

Robust communications system

The Ubiquity Bullet ac system is configured using a spectrum analyser working close to metallic structures. This allows to configure the system to its optimum performance for working surrounded of metallic tanks and other structures common in refineries.

Figure 80. Wireless communication system.

Satellite

The satellite shown in Figure 81 is a magnetic crawler that is deployed from the HYBRID drone to reach difficult to access areas on pipe racks. This includes the underside of pipes, elbows, T-pieces and vertical sections. It is equipped with two cameras for navigation and an ultrasonic roller-probe to perform wall thickness measurements. The two drive modules on each side house brushless DC motors to drive the permanent magnet wheels. Each of the drives is also equipped with a proprietary motor controller. This arrangement allows for highly manoeuvrable differential drive steering. Front and back stabiliser arms extend from the central body. They are mechanically linked and spring loaded to ensure that the roller-probe is kept in perpendicular orientation to the surface.

Figure 81: Satellite description

The satellite robot is tethered to the HYBRID flyer for power supply, ultrasonic analogue signal transfer and ethernet motor control connection as shown in Figure 82. Incremental encoder information for B- and C-Scans are available from the ethernet control interface and can be synthesised from a dedicated encoder out board that feeds incremental encoder information to the UT instrument. The video feed is a wireless radio link between the satellite and a handheld display.

Figure 82: Satellite interfaces

4.2.3 Technical Specifications

Table 12: HYBRID specifications

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
HY-Spec-01	<p>Size of the robot (in mm)</p>
HY-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
HY-Spec-03	Maximum takeoff weight: 15 Kg
HY-Spec-04	Weight with standard equipment and batteries: 12 Kg
HY-Spec-05	Free-flight positioning precision using GNSS: Vertical 0,5 m, horizontal 1,5 m.
HY-Spec-06	Positioning precision using Lidar: Vertical 0,05 m, horizontal 0,05 m
HY-Spec-07	Maximum wind resistance while flying: 10 m/s
HY-Spec-08	Maximum wind resistance while landing on pipe: 4 m/s
HY-Spec-09	Standard configuration flight time: 7 min
HY-Spec-10	Minimum pipe diameter: 8 inches
HY-Spec-11	Batteries specifications: 2 units of 6S (25 V) and 16 Ah capacity.
HY-Spec-12	Wireless communications over proprietary ubiquity Wi-Fi protocol.
HY-Spec-13	Cable communications over ethernet gigabit cable
HY-Spec-14	Satellite speed 100 mm/s
HY-Spec-15	Satellite weight 0.8 kg

HY-Spec-16	Satellite power supply 24 ... 26 V
HY-Spec-17	Satellite maximum power consumption 28.5 W
HY-Spec-18	Satellite Size 138 x 171 x 90 mm
HY-Spec-19	Satellite minimum height clearance 100 mm
HY-Spec-20	Satellite control ethernet interface
HY-Spec-21	Satellite navigation camera resolution HD 1080p
HY-Spec-22	Satellite video 5.8 Ghz A/V interface
HY-Spec-23	Satellite umbilical length 2 m
HY-Spec-24	Satellite protection rating IP 3x
HY-Spec-25	Satellite diameter range for navigation OD 200 ... ID 300 mm
HY-Spec-26	Satellite diameter range for inspection OD 200 ... flat
HY-Spec-27	Satellite maximum Surface temperatura 0 ... 80 °C
HY-Spec-28	Satellite maximum coating thickness 0.3 mm
HY-Spec-29	Satellite UTM thickness range 3 ... 100 mm
HY-Spec-30	Satellite UTM sensor dual crystal with 8 mm element size
HY-Spec-31	Satellite UTM sensor frequency 4 MHz
HY-Spec-32	Satellite UTM Lemo 00 connector

5. Conclusions

This document aimed to describe the first iteration of the robotic vehicles for the PILOTING system. These eight systems were developed to meet the requirements laid out by the ten use-case scenarios described in D3.1. Likewise they are equipped with the perception and processing hardware needed to implement the advanced autonomous functionalities of the I&M platform specified in D3.2.

The report accompanies the actual demonstrators to describe their specifications and design. Although there are a couple of them that are still under manufacturing process, the design of all them is completed and the delay was caused by covid-19 impact in the project activities.

These systems are the foundation for the further development of the I&M platform. This includes the autonomous functionalities and general control stations. They will be utilising mission planning functionalities and generating navigation and inspection data for the database and utilised in visualisation and AI analysis.

The results and learning of the first validation experiments will in turn feed the development of the second and final iteration of the robotic vehicles with its deliverable D4.3 in Month 38.